

OPEN GOVERNMENT DATA AND NFTs. A PROPOSED SOLUTION FOR GOVERNMENTS

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1. Introduction

Governments, like any other organization, have to provide services based on the data produced through administrative tasks. Governments are responsible for making the interactions with local citizens meaningful in the sense of services. This interaction between governments and citizens can be expensive, but at the same time, it should be two-way communication. Two-way communication, nowadays, is only possible with the help of the necessary tools and technologies required to develop eGovernment strategies, policies, and management. Open Government Data (OGD)-based services and products play a role in improving the living standards of citizens. Since the government is not an isolated structure, open government data is highly dynamic and involves stakeholders such as businesses, citizens, and research sectors. Thus, this complex data flow/exchange and, therefore, interoperability among OGD ecosystems is a challenging task (Charalabidis et al., 2016). An important thing that should be considered is the secure, reliable, consistent, and timely movement of data from one entity to another entity. The quadruple helix can be improved by introducing BCT for secure OGD communication, as shown in **Figure 1**. Blockchain technology is an essential aspect of OGD's transparency and accountability by providing secure blocks with a chaining structure. It is possible to employ openness and transparency to improve public service and budget utilization, increase citizen participation, counteract corruption and fraud, and promote public trust in government.

At the same time, BCT appears to be a tendency to include and utilize this technology beyond the scope of cryptocurrency. Although NFTs are best known for being used to produce digital works of art or collector's items, large companies and public administrations have taken advantage of their potential to make other services or products available to the public: 'analog' items such as the deeds to a house, a city's historical heritage or a company's archive, and smart contracts are some examples of this.

The aim of this research is twofold: On one hand to examine the current state of the art regarding BCT and NFTs in the public sector along, with their potential benefits and barriers and on the other hand to combine NFTs and Open Government Data, by proposing an NFT transactions solution for the public sector.

Figure 1. Quadruple helix and BCT-based OD Ecosystem

2. Open Government Data, Blockchain Technology & NFTs

Open Data (OD) is freely available to use and distribute even though for commercial use. There are several other detailed definitions for OD. One of the most appropriate considerations to take into account is the steps needed to be taken from gathering data to completely opening them (**Figure 2**). OD should be complete, fully uploaded, timely for decision-making, primary focus, and mainly collected by experts or researchers. The accessibility refers to their availability on some platforms through APIs or other 5-star formats. Machine readability is an important aspect to consider, although when data is available in csv or xlsx formats, it is considered machine-readable. The data must be non-discriminatory without considering gender or any other factor while opening. Non-proprietary means it must be available under open licensing, which means it can be used and distributed by anyone. Free means that data must be available under the two most commonly used licenses, such as CC-BY and CCO, while publishing the open data. The data also needs to be reviewable to remove outliers, errors, and omissions (E&O) when detected by any end user.

Figure 2. Detailed open data definition

There are three steps/stages involved in the OD plan (**Figure 3**) which are (1) Preparation of OD for publication (2) Launching the OD stage and (3) Extend and sustaining the OD. The preparation stage is a well-defined process where the readiness assessment of the open data is checked by evaluating the technology skills, senior leadership involvement, civic engagement, financing for

OD, data management plan, data demand, policy and legal perspective of OD, and institutions' involvement in OD. After checking their readiness assessment, OD providers build the OD inventory where a mapping between supply and demand is drawn. The legal and policy work is also considered at this stage, such as OD licenses, policies, and legal review. The essential license is selected based on the OD properties and organization rules. The steering committee can be involved to decide better which legal and policy work needs to be more focused on. The last stage refers to the establishment of a data catalog to share the OD with users and the community by means of data curators.

Figure 3. Open data action plan

At all administrative levels, the public sector is one of the largest producers and holders of data and information. In recent years, the size and variety of open data released by public administrations around the world has increased significantly, to the extent that their management is now determined or regulated in many cases, through legislative regulations (Vetrò et al., 2016). Government data is understood as that subset of public data and information produced or collected by the government or government-controlled organizations (Public Agencies and Enterprises). Such data are, for example, applicable laws and circulars, public expenditure, sources of public revenue, etc. (Park et al., 2022). Open government data is essentially a subset of open data and is simply government-related data that is open to the public (Kučera et al., 2013). Several countries have already demonstrated their commitment to open government data by joining the Open Government Partnership (Attard et al., 2015).

Blockchain Technology (BCT, Blockchain as BC) is a piece of software that functions as a ledger distributed across nodes of a communications network. What distinguishes it from other online databases or trading platforms is its immutability since anyone can trade digital assets peer to peer, and no one can alter or undo those transactions without a majority of the network's approval. The main characteristics of BCT, such as its decentralized nature, anonymity of the users, auditability, and others, make it appealing as an infrastructure with great potential but also many challenges. Alexopoulos et al. (2019) conducted a thorough analysis of the benefits and barriers of BCT applications in an eGovernment context and among the key benefits for public services were privacy, data safety, and anonymity (as it is achieved via the usage of private keys). On the other hand, one of the most important challenges was privacy leakage due to the fact that the users' public keys are visible, which can introduce further considerations. On a similar note, Sarantis et al. (2020) investigated BCT in eGovernment and identified fifteen areas in need of related research. Among those areas were data security and privacy, considering identity management and the

protection of personal data with the help of BCT but also under the guidance of concepts such as privacy-by-design and privacy-by-default. Ølnes and Janssen (2018) identified the need to view BCT beyond its currency applications and consider its potential use as an infrastructure or platform for governmental services, such as identity management. They eventually argue that BCT is an emerging platform, as it features decentralized management and control; Ølnes et al. (2017) included the potential benefits and promises of BCT, and under the category “Informational benefits”, where, again, data integrity, higher data quality and privacy, can be found. Ølnes and Jansen (2018) developed a framework with the purpose of understanding and making clearer the benefits and challenges associated with the introduction of BCT in public services. Part of this framework was a proof-of-concept example of a project related to the Norwegian Tax Administration, with the results showing that the developed system “worked as expected; however, the immutability of the documents could be problematic with regards to privacy and the GDPR’s right-to-be-forgotten”. A systematic literature review by Batubara, Ubacht and Jansen (2018) indicated that, however promising, the adoption of BCT for eGovernment lacks empirical evidence and needs further research to target areas such as security, scalability, interoperability, and flexibility. The benefits they see also include improved data integrity, quality, transparency, and privacy; however, they emphasize the need for proper design solutions at an architectural level in order to overcome the identified challenges. Proposed eGovernment systems based on BCT have already been introduced and published, such as the decentralized system based on consortium blockchain technology by Elisa et al. (2019), Alexopoulos et al. (2018).

One type of digital asset is Bitcoin and other cryptocurrencies used in Bitcoin payment networks. Non-fungible tokens are the opposite of these. The term “fungibility” describes the degree to which one asset can be exchanged for another of the same type. Non-fungible assets, in contrast to fungible assets, are valued in a distinct manner due to their specific characteristics and scarcity. Tokens stored on the blockchain that represent non-fungible assets, such as works of art, digital property, or media, are known as NFTs. Whether the item in question is digital or tangible, an NFT can be regarded as a digital certificate of ownership and authenticity that cannot be revoked. There is one unique value represented by each NFT token. No one could reasonably expect to swap out a picture for a different one in a legal agreement without raising suspicions. Antiques or collectibles are just one type of NFT; others include official documents such as birth and death records, property titles, and Internet of Things object identifiers.

The goal of NFT developers was for their creations to be cryptographically verifiable, unique or exceedingly rare, and easy to trade. Using the cryptographic signatures built into the blockchain, the history and present owner of an NFT may be determined in an instant. Because of their adaptability, NFTs can be utilized as substitutes for a wide range of real-world, virtual, and ethereal assets. Digital works of art, digital collectibles, media files, event tickets, smart contracts, and video game assets are the most common NFT assets.

3. The proposed solution

The proposed solution provides transparency and openness on public sector financial movements produced by administrative tasks. In particular, there are three financial movements (or phases):

- The approval decision for a supply or, in general, for some expenditure,

- The commitment decision which commits the budget for the approval decision, and,
- The payment decision after the completeness of payment for the supply or expenditure.

For this purpose, Governments need to build a Government BC in which they will have at least three “Government Wallets”, the Main Wallet, the Commitment Wallet, and the Payment Wallet. The Main Wallet is responsible for keeping the approval decisions, the Commitment Wallet is responsible for keeping the commitments decision, and the Payments Wallet is responsible for keeping the payments decision (proofs) after the completeness of the original payment.

The Main Wallet represents the summary of each public organisation’s money source, meaning that each public organisation owns its own Main Wallet. At the same time, each VAT number (Citizens, Businesses, etc.) has its own wallet. The Main Wallet and/or each public sector wallet can produce the decisions (Centralized mint), as NFTs, and store the decision in this wallet until the first transaction is made.

During the approval decision, the NFT transferred from the Main Wallet to the Approval Wallet. The same procedure comes for the commitment movement as well. Finally, the payment decision (NFT) is transferred to the VAT number wallet.

The majority of NFTs transactions reside on the Government’s cryptocurrency’s BC, a distributed public ledger that records transactions. NFTs are individual tokens with valuable information stored in them. The transactions’ decisions are stored on the blockchain, but the payments are carried out through bank transfers (same as nowadays). These transactions need to be validated and stored in a block. At the same time, the consensus mechanism for Government BC will be Proof-of-Stake (PoS) to be more energy efficient since Proof-of-Work (PoW) is not energy efficient. Under PoS, Block creators are called validators. A validator checks transactions, verifies activity, votes on outcomes, and maintains records. In return, Validators receive a yearly amount depending on their stake. Under PoW, block creators are called miners. Miners work to solve the hash, a cryptographic number, to verify transactions. In return for solving the hash, they are rewarded with a coin. A Validator is any entity (stakeholder) owning a wallet capable of creating the next block (generate) on the Government’s cryptocurrency’s blockchain to store the transactions (Decentralized). Validators’ wallets are rewarded with government tokens (cryptocurrency).

Government tokens can be redeemed for either discounts on buying goods from green companies that collaborate with governments that foster green sustainable development (electric cars and bicycles) or buying services provided by the public sector (e.g., public gyms, public bicycle rental, etc).

Furthermore, Users can transfer government tokens between their wallets. The redeemed tokens from stakeholders are automatically burned in a burn address. A burn address is a digital wallet that can't be accessed because it doesn't have a private key attached to it, like a lock that someone never built a keyhole for.

The max supply will be infinite, as a pegged coin in order to keep the price as low as it is possible, since the use of this coin is for non-profit reasons. Because of the selected consensus mechanism, at the start of this BC all VAT number wallets will receive 10.000 tokens in order to have the

validation ability. A Validator must have at least 100 tokens in the wallet. Validators can get annual returns between 15% to 30% depending on the Government Tokens they stake. The algorithm may be changed if any new algorithm, less energy efficient, is discovered.

4. Discussion

Eight basic principles are described in the literature (Höchtel and Reichstädter, 2011; Solar et al., 2013), which should meet government data in order to be considered open. These are: (1) Complete; (2) Primary; (3) Timely; (4) Accessible; (5) Machine processable; (6) Non-discriminatory; (7) Non-proprietary; (8) License-free. In parallel, Government data may contain multiple sets of data, including transactions in any form (e.g. financial or not) and expenditure, population, census, parliamentary proceedings, etc. According to Ubaldi (2013) public data sets included in open government data initiatives include:

- 1.business information (including chamber of commerce information, etc.)
- 2.registries, patent and trademark information and public databases
- 3.geographic information (such as address information, aerial photographs, buildings, geology, and topographic information)
- 4.legal information (such as national, and international court decisions, national laws)
- 5.meteorological information (including data and models for climate and weather forecasts)
- 6.social data (such as statistics on the economy, employment, health, population etc.).
- 7.Transport information (such as traffic congestion, public transport and vehicle classification);

At the same time, the characteristics of NFTs (as it is mentioned above) along with their usage advantages (ownership, authenticity, transferability, creation of economic opportunity, and boosting inclusive growth), constitute them as an innovative solution for governments. The adoption of NFTs solutions by the public sector will not only provide many new capabilities and better services but will establish a safest, openly accessible, transparent and eco-friendly transactional environment. In addition the most important disadvantage of the NFTs usage which is the Concerns Regarding Ecological Impact, seems that fades due to the Proof-of-Stake consensus mechanisms which is proven to be energy efficiency.

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